

Supporting Information for

Extracting the temperature dependence of both nanowire resistivity and junction resistance from electrical measurements on printed silver nanowire networks

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Contents

S1: Silver Nanowire Size Analysis	S3
S2: Problems with the Impedance Spectroscopy Method.....	S6
S3: Literature Bloch-Grüneisen Fitting Parameters Comparison	S7
References.....	S8

S1: Silver Nanowire Size Analysis

Figure S1: (A-F) SEM histograms of l_{NW} for AgNWs with a 38nm diameter having increasing sonication times of (A) 0, (B) 0.25, (C) 0.5, (D) 1, (E) 1.5 and (F) 2 hours.

Figure S2: (A-F) SEM histograms of l_{NW} for AgNWs with a 57nm diameter having increasing sonication times of (A) 0, (B) 0.25, (C) 0.5, (D) 1, (E) 1.5 and (F) 2 hours.

Figure S3: (A-F) SEM histograms of D_{NW} for AgNWs labelled **(A)** 38nm and **(B)** 57nm throughout this study.

S2: Problems with the Impedance Spectroscopy Method

It is not yet clear how broadly applicable the impedance spectroscopy technique to measure R_J , C_J and R_{NS}^I is and what other materials it can be extended to. This procedure models the combination of a nanoparticle and junction as a so-called Randles circuit: a resistor, R_N , representing the nanoparticle, in series with a parallel resistor/capacitor pair representing the junction resistance, R_J , and capacitance, C_J . The presence of the capacitor causes features to appear at high frequency (typically $>10^6$ rad/s) in the impedance spectra which can be fitted using equivalent circuit models to give R_N , R_J , and C_J . However, in practice such features can only be fitted when $(R_J C_J)^{-1} < \omega_{Max}$ where ω_{Max} is the highest angular frequency accessible to the impedance spectrometer. In ref 1 MoS₂ networks displayed $(R_J C_J)^{-1}$ values of $\sim 10^7$ rad/s, making them accessible to good impedance spectrometers. However, networks of conducting nanoparticles will have much lower junction resistances. In all likelihood this will increase $(R_J C_J)^{-1}$ outside the accessible range of most impedance spectrometers. Thus, an alternative method is required to simultaneously interrogate both intra- and inter-particle transport mechanisms in nanonets.

S3: Literature Bloch-Grüneisen Fitting Parameters Comparison

Reference	D_{NW} (nm)	Network/ Single Nanowire	Θ_D (K)	ρ_0 ($10^{-9} \Omega \text{ m}$)	α_{e-ph} ($10^{-8} \Omega \text{ m}$)
Bulk Silver			235	0.01	5.24
Zhao ²	84	Nanowire	128	1.67	3.47
Zhao ²	38	Nanowire	173	6.0	5.02
Cheng ³	227	Nanowire	151	3.25	9.91
Kojda ⁴	150	Nanowire	215	2.04	6.06
He 2018 ⁵	210	Nanowire	199	162	10.8
This Work	38	Network	181	8.9	9.6
This Work	57	Network	133	4.8	3.0

Table S1: Table comparing fitting parameters for the Bloch-Grüneisen equation for various sources found in literature.

References

- (1) Gabbett, C.; Kelly, A.; Coleman, E.; Doolan, L.; Carey, T.; Synnatschke, K.; Liu, S.; Dawson, A.; O'Suilleabhain, D.; Munuera, J.; et al. Understanding how junction resistances impact the conduction mechanism in nano-networks. *NATURE COMMUNICATIONS* **2024**, *15*, Article. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-024-48614-5.
- (2) Zhao, Y.; Fitzgerald, M. L.; Tao, Y.; Pan, Z. L.; Sauti, G.; Xu, D. Y.; Xu, Y. Q.; Li, D. Y. Electrical and Thermal Transport through Silver Nanowires and Their Contacts: Effects of Elastic Stiffening. *Nano Letters* **2020**, *20* (10), 7389-7396, Article. DOI: 10.1021/acs.nanolett.0c02014.
- (3) Cheng, Z.; Liu, L. J.; Xu, S.; Lu, M.; Wang, X. W. Temperature Dependence of Electrical and Thermal Conduction in Single Silver Nanowire. *Scientific Reports* **2015**, *5*, 12. DOI: 10.1038/srep10718.
- (4) Kojda, D.; Mitdank, R.; Handweg, M.; Mogilatenko, A.; Albrecht, M.; Wang, Z.; Ruhhammer, J.; Kroener, M.; Woias, P.; Fischer, S. F. Temperature-dependent thermoelectric properties of individual silver nanowires. *Physical Review B* **2015**, *91* (2), 13, Article. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevB.91.024302.
- (5) He, G. C.; Lu, H.; Dong, X. Z.; Zhang, Y. L.; Liu, J.; Xie, C. Q.; Zhao, Z. S. Electrical and thermal properties of silver nanowire fabricated on a flexible substrate by two- beam laser direct writing for designing a thermometer. *Rsc Advances* **2018**, *8* (44), 24893-24899. DOI: 10.1039/c8ra03280g.